

LEGAL ASPECTS OF INFLUENCER ADVERTISING IN RUSSIA

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Abstract

The article examines the legal aspects of influencer advertising in Russia. The evolving regulatory framework is analyzed, focusing on compliance challenges. It is emphasized that transparency, consumer protection, and national security concerns are central to this legal landscape. The analysis highlights the significant responsibilities placed on influencers and brands. The proactive role of regulatory bodies in enforcing compliance is also discussed, underscoring the importance of adherence to evolving legal standards.

Keywords: influencer marketing, Russian law, advertising regulation, data protection, legal challenges, social media, digital advertising.

Introduction

Influencer marketing has emerged as a powerful tool for brand promotion in Russia, reflecting global trends where digital influencers play a pivotal role in shaping consumer behavior. This form of marketing, characterized by the collaboration between brands and individuals with significant social media followings, has proven highly effective in engaging target audiences. However, the rapid expansion of influencer marketing has also brought to light a range of legal challenges, particularly concerning the regulation of advertising practices within this domain.

The legal landscape governing influencer advertising in Russia is complex and evolving. It intersects with various branches of law, including advertising law, consumer protection, intellectual property, and digital media regulations. The growing significance of influencers as a marketing medium has necessitated the development of specific legal frameworks to ensure transparency, fairness, and accountability in advertising practices. Understanding the legal nuances of influencer marketing in Russia is important for both marketers and legal practitioners.

The primary objective of this article is to explore the legal aspects of influencer advertising in Russia, with a focus on the existing regulatory framework, the challenges of compliance, and the implications for stakeholders involved in the influencer marketing ecosystem.

Main part. Regulatory environment for influencer advertising in Russia

An influencer is an individual who has established credibility and a substantial following in a specific niche, often using social media platforms to shape the opinions and behaviors of their audience. Influencers leverage their authenticity and reach to promote products or services, typically through partnerships with brands, making them key players in digital marketing.

According to the July 2024 ranking by the company «Medialogia», popular Russian influencers have a monthly audience reach of up to 1,5 million people [1]. The average advertising expenditure per internet user in the influencer market amounts to \$1,47 [2]. It is projected that advertising expenditures will total \$192,5 million for the year 2024.

Pic. 1. Annual growth rates of influencer advertising expenditures, million dollars

The legal framework governing influencer advertising in Russia is rooted in a broader set of laws and regulations that control advertising practices across various media. Central to this framework is the **Federal Law «On Advertising»** (No. 38-FZ), which establishes the foundational principles for advertising in Russia, including requirements for truthfulness,

fairness, and non-deceptiveness [3]. This law applies universally to all forms of advertising, encompassing traditional media, digital platforms, and, by extension, influencer marketing.

Any advertisement, including those disseminated by influencers, must be clearly identifiable as such. The law requires that promotional content be distinguished

from regular content to prevent misleading consumers. This is crucial in influencer marketing, where the line between personal opinions and paid endorsements can often blur. Influencers are required to disclose any commercial relationships they have with brands, typically through clear labeling of posts as «advertising» or using appropriate hashtags (e.g., #ad, #sponsored) to ensure transparency. Under the **ERID** (Electronic Register of Advertising) system, advertisers must register all advertisements, including those made through influencers, to ensure proper monitoring and compliance. This system requires advertisers to submit detailed information about the advertising content, including the identities of the advertisers and influencers involved, as well as the terms of the promotion.

The legal framework for influencer advertising in Russia was further tightened in 2024 with amendments to the **Federal Law «On Communications»** (No. 126-FZ). This legislation requires bloggers and administrators of channels with an audience exceeding 10,000 subscribers, who post endorsements, to submit their personal data to Roskomnadzor, the Federal Service for Supervision of Communications, Information Technology, and Mass Media [4]. This requirement applies even to blogs and channels hosted on platforms banned in Russia. Furthermore, the law extends beyond individuals, covering legal entities and brands as well. However, how influencers (blogs and channels) will submit their information to the regulator remains unclear. The primary objective of this law is to ensure the verification and identification of users. Influencers who fail to comply with these data submission requirements will be prohibited from placing advertisements. Other users will be prohibited from reposting content from these non-compliant channels.

Social network administrators will be required to restrict access to the personal pages of users who do not comply with these data submission requirements within 24 hours of receiving a request from Roskomnadzor. This provision will come into effect on January 1, 2025. Social networks with a daily audience of more than 500,000 users will also be required to provide user information upon request by Roskomnadzor or the Federal Security Service (FSB).

Another significant legal aspect of influencer advertising in Russia is the prohibition on placing advertisements with foreign agents, as stipulated by the amendments to the **Federal Law «On Advertising»** introduced in 2024 [3]. The law aims to limit the influence of organizations and individuals deemed to represent foreign interests, ensuring that advertising activities within Russia align with national security and public interest objectives. In 2024, a legislative bill was also passed prohibiting advertising on social networks that have been designated as extremist organizations.

This law further tightens the regulatory environment for digital advertising in Russia, aiming to prevent the dissemination of content through platforms that are considered to pose a threat to national security.

Other relevant legal provisions include the **Law «On Consumer Protection»** (No. 2300-1), which provides additional safeguards for consumers by prohibiting unfair commercial practices [5]. This law is particularly pertinent to influencer advertising, as it addresses issues related to misleading information, false claims, and the overall accuracy of promotional content. The **Civil Code of the Russian Federation** plays a role in regulating contractual relationships between influencers and brands, including issues of intellectual property, copyright, and liability [6].

The enforcement of these regulations is primarily overseen by the **Federal Antimonopoly Service** (FAS), which serves as the principal regulatory body for advertising practices in Russia. The FAS is responsible for monitoring compliance with advertising laws and has the authority to investigate potential violations, issue warnings, and impose penalties. In recent years, the FAS has increasingly focused on influencer marketing, recognizing its growing impact on consumer behavior. The agency has issued several guidelines and clarifications specifically addressing influencer advertising, emphasizing the need for transparency and adherence to the legal requirements [7].

The FAS collaborates with other regulatory bodies, such as the Roskomnadzor, which oversees digital and media compliance, including the use of social media platforms by influencers. This multi-agency approach ensures a comprehensive oversight of influencer advertising, addressing not only the content of advertisements but also the platforms through which they are disseminated.

Legal complexities in influencer advertising in Russia

Influencer marketing, while an increasingly popular and effective strategy for brand promotion, presents several legal challenges within the Russian regulatory framework. These challenges arise from the evolving nature of digital marketing, the unique dynamics of influencer-audience interactions, and the need to align marketing practices with established legal standards [8]. As influencer marketing continues to grow, it becomes crucial to understand and address the key legal issues that can impact both influencers and brands operating in Russia. The legal complexities associated with influencer advertising range from transparency and disclosure requirements to intellectual property rights, contractual obligations, and potential liabilities. These challenges necessitate careful navigation to ensure compliance with the law and to mitigate risks.

Table 1

Key legal challenges in influencer advertising in Russia [9, 10]

Legal challenge	Description	Regulatory reference	Implications
IP rights	Issues related to the use of copyrighted material, trademarks, and proprietary content in influencer posts.	Civil Code of the Russian Federation	Unauthorized use can result in legal action from rights holders, including fines and removal of content.
Liability for misleading advertising	Influencers and brands can be held accountable for false or misleading claims made in advertisements.	Federal Law on Advertising (No. 38-FZ)	Legal consequences include fines, content removal, and potential damage to consumer trust.
Compliance with ERID	Mandatory registration of all advertisements with the Electronic Register of Advertising (ERID).	ERID regulations, overseen by the FAS	Non-compliance can result in fines and restrictions on future advertising activities.
Data protection and privacy	Compliance with data protection laws when handling personal data of followers or customers.	Federal Law on Personal Data (No. 152-FZ)	Violations can lead to significant fines and legal actions from affected individuals.
Content platform regulations	Influencer content must comply with platform-specific rules and Russian media laws.	Federal Law on Information, IT, and Information Protection	Content that violates platform rules or Russian law can be removed, and accounts may be suspended.
Taxation and Financial Reporting	Influencers must report income from advertising and adhere to tax regulations.	Russian Tax Code	Failure to comply with tax obligations can result in fines, penalties, and legal proceedings.

The recently enacted Russian legal framework for social media endorsements presents several questions and challenges, such as the fluctuating number of followers tied to the obligation to submit personal data to Roskomnadzor, the ambiguous regulation of registered violations, and the lack of clarity in the warning system.

According to the author, the legal landscape for influencer advertising in Russia presents a complex array of challenges that require careful navigation by both influencers and brands. Ensuring that cross-border campaigns adhere to Russian laws, while also respecting the legal requirements of other countries, necessitates a high level of legal expertise and strategic planning [11].

Comparison with international practices

The regulation of influencer advertising varies significantly across different jurisdictions, reflecting diverse approaches to balancing consumer protection, transparency, and the evolving nature of digital marketing. Comparing Russia's legal framework with international practices highlights both commonalities and divergences that offer valuable insights for brands and influencers operating in a global environment.

In the **European Union (EU)**, influencer advertising is primarily governed by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Unfair Commercial Practices Directive (UCPD). The GDPR imposes strict rules on the processing of personal data, which affects how influencers manage and use follower information, particularly in targeted advertising. The UCPD mandates that all commercial communications must be clearly identifiable as such, a principle similar

to Russia's requirements for transparency and disclosure under the Federal Law on Advertising.

In the **United States**, the Federal Trade Commission (FTC) plays a central role in regulating influencer advertising. The FTC's guidelines require that influencers clearly disclose any material connections with brands, such as sponsorships or free products, to avoid misleading consumers. These disclosures must be clear and conspicuous, typically achieved through hashtags like #ad or #sponsored, much like the requirements in Russia. However, the FTC also provides detailed guidance on what constitutes adequate disclosure, emphasizing the need for transparency in all forms of digital marketing. The FTC's enforcement actions against non-compliant influencers and brands serve as a deterrent, promoting adherence to these guidelines.

When comparing these international practices with Russia's regulatory environment, several key themes emerge. Russia's approach, like that of the EU and the United States, emphasizes transparency and consumer protection, with specific requirements for disclosing commercial relationships in influencer marketing [12]. However, Russia's legal framework also incorporates elements of state control and surveillance, as seen in the mandatory registration of influencers with Roskomnadzor and the prohibition of advertising on platforms deemed extremist or foreign agents. This blend of consumer protection and state oversight distinguishes Russia's regulatory environment from those in the EU and the United States, where the focus is more on consumer rights and less on state control. Brands and influencers operating in Russia must be particularly mindful of these distinctive elements, ensuring that their marketing

strategies are not only effective but also fully compliant with the country's complex legal framework.

Analysis of judicial practice in cases of advertising law violations

The enforcement of advertising laws in Russia has become increasingly rigorous, with judicial practices playing a crucial role in shaping the legal landscape. Recent court cases involving violations of advertising regulations, particularly in the context of digital and influencer marketing, have highlighted the judiciary's commitment to upholding legal standards and protecting consumer rights.

In 2023, the Chelyabinsk Office of the FAS of Russia issued a ruling on an administrative offense against an individual for disseminating advertising on the social network «VKontakte» within the community «Let's eat together. Chelyabinsk» in the form of a post. It was found that the post exhibited signs of violating Part 16, Article 18.1 of the Federal Law «On Advertising» and Part 1, Article 14.3 of the Code of Administrative Offenses, specifically the placement of information without the «advertisement» label [13]. The post possessed qualifying characteristics of an advertisement: it was addressed to an undefined audience, aimed at attracting attention and maintaining interest in the advertised object. An administrative fine of 2,000 rubles was imposed.

One of the most notable cases was that of Elena Lisovskaya, the author of the channel «Lisa Rules». In 2023, she was held administratively liable for failing to comply with the requirements of Article 18.1 of the Law «On Advertising», specifically for posting three entries without an advertising identifier on the Telegram channel «Lisa Rules». The fine amounted to 100,000 rubles for each post [14].

In the first four months of 2024, the total amount of fines imposed on bloggers, intermediaries, and advertisers for violations of legislation exceeded 4.5 million rubles. Of the 75 rulings issued, 29 were for the absence of an identifier, and 46 were for failure to provide complete and accurate information. For comparison, only four rulings were issued in the entire year of 2023 [15]. The sharp rise in fines highlights the authorities' intensified focus on ensuring transparency and accountability in online activities. In the foreseeable future, reflecting a broader effort to bring digital practices in line with established legal frameworks.

Conclusions

The legal landscape governing influencer advertising in Russia presents a multifaceted and evolving framework that imposes significant responsibilities on influencers and brands. The regulatory environment is characterized by stringent requirements designed to ensure transparency, consumer protection, and adherence to national security concerns. Central to this framework are the Federal Law on Advertising and the ERID system, which mandate clear disclosure of promotional content and the registration of advertisements. The recent amendments to laws concerning data protection and the restriction of advertisements by foreign agents further tighten the regulatory controls, reflecting a heightened emphasis on state oversight.

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